

A study of perspectives on cultural dimensions and employee performance in Zimbabwe State Universities

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to explore the effect of cultural dimensions on employee productivity in Zimbabwe state universities. Many studies have been done to establish the impact of organisational culture on company performance. However, a few studies were done to investigate the relationship between cultural dimensions and employee performance in the education sector. The themes of the study were quantified in terms of four cultural dimensions, such as power distance, individualism, uncertainty avoidance and masculinity. The questionnaire approach was used to collect primary data from 400 employees of thirteen public universities in Zimbabwe. Data was analysed using the ANOVA and Pearson's correlation Matrix. The results of the study revealed that there is a positive relationship between cultural dimension and employee productivity.

Keywords: Cultural dimensions, employee performance, state universities, employee productivity, education sector.

INTRODUCTION

Zimbabwe has thirteen public universities and four private universities. The first university in Zimbabwe was the University of Zimbabwe and was established in 1957 (Shizha, 2011). In 1980 the government of Zimbabwe embarked on a massive expansion of

university education (Nherera, 2000). In 1991 the National University of Science and Technology was born and this was followed by the establishment of the Bindura University of Science Education (BUSE) in 1996 and Zimbabwe Open University (ZOU) in 1998 (Shizha, 2011).

Table 1: A list of universities in Zimbabwe

University	Public/Private	Year Established
1. University of Zimbabwe	Public	1957
2. National University of Science and Technology (NUST)	Public	1991
3. Africa university	Private	1992
4. Solusi University	Private	1994
5. Bindura University of Science Education (BUSE)	Public	1996
6. Zimbabwe Open University (ZOU)	Public	1998
7. Midlands State University	Public	1999
8. Catholic University in Zimbabwe (CUZ)	Private	2001
9. Reformed Church in Zimbabwe (RCU)	Private	2001
10. Chinhoyi University of Technology (CUT)	Public	2001
11. Great Zimbabwe University (GZU)	Public	2002
12. Women's University in Africa (WUA)	Private	2004
13. Lupane State University (LSU)	Public	2004
14. Harare Institute of Technology	Public	2005
15. Zimbabwe Ezekiel Guti University (ZEGU)	Private	2010
16. Gwanda State University (GSU)	Public	2012
17. Manicaland University of Applied Sciences (MUAS)	Public	2014
18. Marondera University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology (MUAST)	Public	2015
19. The Zimbabwe National Defence University (ZNDU)	Public	2016

Source: Shizha (2011).

Universities in Zimbabwe are governed by Councils appointed by the Minister in charge of Higher Education and in terms of the Act of Parliament (for example, the National University of Science and Technology Act of 1990). University Councils make policy and the day to day running of the organisation is done by the Vice Chancellor and the management team. The university senate is the supreme organ that makes operational policy and strategy and the organ is chaired by the Vice Chancellor or one of the Pro-Vice Chancellors. The doctrine of both the council and the senate are supported by a myriad of university committees and subcommittees. The system of councils, the senate, committees and sub-committees provide the corporate governance needed by the university. University Deans are given the responsibility of managing the relevant Faculties while university departments are managed by chairpersons appointed by the Vice Chancellor in consultation with departmental board members. In 2006 the Zimbabwe Council for Higher Education (ZIMCHE) was established in order to manage quality assurance issues in Universities and to enhance employee productivity. The government has the responsibility of funding all state universities using funds from the fiscus. These contributions constitute almost 95% of

the recurrent expenditure and 100% of the capital expenditure. Therefore, employee productivity issues are significant because state universities are using public funds.

THE REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

According to Mathis and Jackson, (2009) the concept of employee performance refers to a family of concepts such as output quality, output quantity, the time-frame within which inputs are turned into outputs, and efficient and effective use of resources. Therefore, employee performance is the capacity of the employees to complete a given task successfully and to produce outputs that are measured and accepted by the supervisors as meeting the required standards.

According to Kenney (1992), employee performance is related to the objectives set by the company. The objectives represent the performance standards. Thus employee performance can be quantified (measured) in terms of production levels, effectiveness, efficiency, quality and profitability. Singh and Mohanty (2012:88) argue that productivity refers to a log of net sales over the total number of employees. Employee productivity refers to employee

performance as measured by output per unit of input. In other words, employee productivity measures the relationship between inputs and outputs.

There are several factors that affect employee performance. These factors are quality of leadership, organisational culture, work environment and training (Hofstede, 1991; Northouse, 2007; Harrison, 2000). The literature on leadership styles has shown that autocratic leaders are not capable of motivating employees to work harder (Armstrong, 2009). Organisational culture refers to the beliefs, values and behaviours that are needed by the organisation to enhance productivity or employee performance (Schein, 1990). The working environment which is supported by positive reward systems, profit sharing mechanisms and job enrichment practices motivate employees to direct both their physical and emotional sacrifices towards the achievement of set goals (Calsen, 2003). The literature on employee performance shows that employee training and development is intended to achieve three objectives, namely:

1. To increase employee productivity.
2. To achieve the goals set by the organisation, and

3. To retain profitable employee (Belcourt et al, 2000).

Definitions of Culture

Taylor (1871) defines culture as “a complex whole which includes knowledge, beliefs, art, morals, law, custom and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society.” Hofstede (1997) refers to culture as “the software of the mind, similar to a computer programme that controls behaviour.” Accordingly, organisational culture refers to “the embodiment of its collective systems, beliefs, norms, ideologies, myths and rituals” that motivate workers to become more efficient and effective on the workplace (Sudarsanam, 2010). Hofstedes (1980, 1987) quantified culture in terms of four dimensions that affect employee performance in most organisations today. These dimensions include; individualism, collectivism, power distance, uncertainty avoidance and masculinity-femininity. **Table 2**, shows the various cultural dimensions and their meaning:

Table 2: Culture dimensions and meaning

Cultural dimension	Meaning
1. Individualism-collectivism	Individualism creates autocratic leaders in the workplace whereas collectivism focuses on group interests and workplace democracy.
2. Power distance	In many organisations, superiors do not want to be criticised because they believe that they have a right to be feared and to be respected. In such organisations employees are treated as machines for production.
3. Uncertainty avoidance	In some organisations, employees are burdened by a myriad of rules, regulations and procedures. In such organisations, employee creativity is compromised.
4. Masculinity-femininity	The thrust of most organisations today is on gender equality and empowerment. More and more women are now employed to do those jobs that used to be dominated by men. However, the relationship between gender equality in employment and employee productivity is yet to be established.

Hofstede (1997).

The Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual framework
Source: Hofstede (1997)

Research Objectives

1. To investigate the effect of collectivism on employee performance.
2. To establish the effect of power distance on employee performance.
3. To find out the effects of uncertainty avoidance on employee performance.
4. To explore the effect of masculinity-femininity on employee performance.

Hypothesis

- H₁** There is a positive relationship between individualism-collectivism and employee performance.
- H₂** There is a positive relationship between power-distance and employee performance.
- H₃** There is a positive relationship between uncertainty avoidance and employee performance.

- H₄** There is a positive relationship between masculinity-femininity and employee performance.

THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used the explanatory quantitative research design to investigate the effect of various cultural dimensions on employee performance. Therefore, the questionnaire approach was used to collect primary data from 400 university employees. The convenient sampling technique was used to collect data from university employees who had a work experience of more than five years. The questionnaire consisted of both open and closed ended questions to ensure the reliability and the validity of the data collected. Data was analysed using a variety of methods, such as descriptive, correlation and regression analysis.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std Deviation
Collectivism-individualism	106	1.763	0.5444
Power Distance	106	1.763	0.5344
Uncertainty avoidance	106	1.763	0.5266
Masculinity-femininity	106	1.763	0.5222
Validity N (listwise).	106		

Table 3, shows that the average mean for collectivism-individualism is 1.763 while the standard deviation is 0.5444. The average mean for power distance is 1.763 while the standard deviation is 0.5344. The average mean for uncertainty avoidance is 1.763 while the standard deviation is 0.5266. The average mean for

masculinity-femininity is 1.763 while the standard deviation is 0.5222. The results seem to suggest that the four cultural dimensions are not significant drivers of employee performance in Public Universities in Zimbabwe.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix

		Employee performance	Collectivism-individualism	Power distance
Employee performance	Pearson correlation	1	0.566**	0.633**
	Sig (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000
	N	106	106	106
Collectivism-individualism	Pearson correlation	0.566**	1	0.733**
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000
	N	106	106	106
Power distance	Pearson correlation	0.633**	0.733**	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	
	N	106	106	106

Table 5: Correlation Matrix

		Employee performance	Collectivism-individualism	Power distance
Employee performance	Pearson correlation	1	0.633	0.733
	Sig (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000
	N	106	106	106
Uncertainty avoidance	Pearson correlation	0.633**	1	0.733**
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000
	N	106	106	106
Masculinity-femininity	Pearson correlation	0.6777	0.733	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	106	106	106

** Correlation is significant at 0.000(2-tailed).

Table 6: Regression coefficients

	Understanding coefficients		Standardised coefficients	t	Sig	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	• 344	• 136		2.611	• 014		
Collectivism-individualism	• 097	• 091	• 111	1.044	• 298	• 456	2.222
Power distance	• 077	• 118	• 066	• 066	• 376	• 333	3.166
Uncertainty avoidance	• 543	• 122	• 564	4.666	• 001	• 333	2.877
Masculinity-femininity	• 188	• 086	• 178	1.723	• 060	• 443	2.466

Table 4 shows that collectivism – individualism correlates positively with employee performance and the relationship between the independent and the dependent variable is supported by the value of 0.566. Power distance is positively correlated with employee performance and the relationship between the variables is strong with the value of 0.633. Uncertainty avoidance has a positive correlation with employee performance and the strong relationship is supported by the value of 0.633. Masculinity –femininity correlates positively with employee performance and relationship is strong at 0.777.

Table 6 shows that collectivism-individualism beta coefficient value is pegged at 0.111 and the insignificant

value of 0.298 is greater than 0.05, here it can be concluded that collectivism-individualism has positive insignificant effect on employee performance. Power distance beta coefficient value is 0.066 and has insignificant value of 0.376 which is greater than 0.05, hence it can be concluded that power distance has a positive insignificant effect on employee performance. Uncertainty avoidance beta coefficient value is 0.564 with a significant value of 0.001 which is less than 0.05, hence it can be concluded that uncertainty avoidance has a positive significant effect on employee performance. Masculinity-femininity beta coefficient value is 0.178 and the significant value of 0.060 is greater than 0.05, hence it can be concluded that

masculinity-femininity has a positive insignificant effect on employee performance.

CONCLUSION

Research on culture and employee performance is critical to the survival of modern organisations. Authorities in public universities have to think globally. Employees in public universities come from different cultures. Culture controls the beliefs, attitudes and the values that employees bring into the organisation. Therefore university authorities must understand the cultural backgrounds of the people they are employing. The results of this study demonstrated that culture has a positive influence on employee performance. This study focussed on four cultural dimensions, such as collectivism-individualism; power distance; uncertainty avoidance; and masculinity and femininity. However, this study did not examine other human resources practises such as, resistance to change, and its effect on employee performance. It is strongly suggested that further studies could be conducted on the interesting subject.

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